

A Note on Phytochemical Investigation of Roots of *Terminalia tomentosa*

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Terminalia tomentosa (Combretaceae) has been found to be medicinally important¹. Several compounds have been isolated from this plant². Now we report isolation and identification of ellagic acid and leucocyanidin from roots of the plant.

The air-dried roots of *T. tomentosa* were defatted and extracted with methanol. The methanol extract was fractionated with solvents of increasing polarity. The ethyl acetate fraction on concentration deposited a solid which was refractionated into ethyl acetate-soluble and -insoluble portions. The insoluble portion on repeated crystallisation with pyridine gave a solid, which was characterised as ellagic acid. The soluble portion on repeated crystallisation with petroleum ether and ethyl acetate gave a creamish white solid, characterised as leucocyanidin.

Ellagic acid : From the pyridine-soluble fraction, a compound, m.p. 360°, m/z M^+ 302 (100%), was isolated whose analytical data were consistent with the molecular formula $C_{14}H_6O_8$. The ^{13}C nmr spectra (ppm) revealed peaks at δ 160.53, 150.81, 141.87, 138.99, 113.74 and 111.99, 108.97. The quarternary signal at δ 113.74 suggests lactone substituted aryl carbon and tetracyclic nature of the compound. From the physical and spectral data, it is considered to be ellagic acid³ which was also revealed from the comparison of its physical data in literature.

Leucocyanidin : The creamish white solid on hydrolysis (ethanolic HCl) gave a product which responded to colour tests of cyanidin⁴. The spectral data (ν_{max} 3 200, 1 610, 1 440, 1 300–1 200, 1 110–1 050 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 278 nm) and comparison of the compound with an authentic sample confirmed the identity of the compound as leucocyanidin.

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